

Acceptable loss: Fitness consequences of salinity-induced cell death in a halotolerant microalga

Running title: Fitness of cell death

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This is the supplementary material regarding this article.

Supplementary material Tables

Table S1: Artificial sea water composition.

	Hyper-saline water	Hypo-saline water
Volume H ₂ O (L)	1	1
NaCl (g)	280,512	-
NA ₂ SO ₄ (g)	3,550	3,550
KCl (g)	0,599	0,599
NAHCO ₃ (g)	0,174	0,174
KBr (g)	0,086	0,086
H ₃ BO ₃ (g)	0,023	0,023
NaF (g)	0,003	0,003
MgCl, 6H ₂ O (g)	9,592	9,592
CaCl ₂ , 2H ₂ O (g)	1,344	1,344
SrCl ₂ , 6H ₂ O (g)	0,022	0,022

Each saline solution was subjected to autoclave sterilisation and were afterwards added with 2% of Guillard's F/2 nutritive medium.

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Table S2: Initial decline (1-hour post-transfer) against type of salinity transfer (experiment 1).

Colonne1	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr (> z)	Population reduction (%)
Intercept (Strain A in Transfer 2.4 to 4M)	-1.185	0.035	-34.050	<2e-16 ***	69
Strain_C	1.309	0.049	26.690	<2e-16 ***	-13
Transfer_2.4to2.4M	1.167	0.049	23.790	<2e-16 ***	2
Transfer_4to4M	1.125	0.055	20.520	<2e-16 ***	6
Strain_C:Transfer_2.4to2.4M	-1.190	0.069	-17.180	<2e-16 ***	-13
Strain_C:Transfer_4to4M	-1.190	0.073	-16.200	<2e-16 ***	-13

GLM on population density on day 0 relative to the expected initial density. We tested the effect of the different levels of salinity transfers and strain identity on demographic decline on the logarithmic scale (from the log link function in the GLM), and also report the population size reduction (where negative values denote proportional increase). p-value: ***: <0.001 ; **: <0.01 ; : <0.05 ; .: <0.1

Table S3: Maximal population growth rate against type of salinity transfer (experiment 1).

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr (> z)
Intercept (Strain A in Transfer 2.4M to 4M, day 1)	8.607	0.070	123.244	< 2e-16 ***
Time	0.638	0.021	30.299	< 2e-16 ***
Strain_C	2.038	0.099	20.652	< 2e-16 ***
Transfer_2.4to2.4M	2.084	0.099	21.125	< 2e-16 ***
Transfer_4to4M	2.107	0.110	19.106	< 2e-16 ***
Time:Strain_C	-0.374	0.030	-12.591	< 2e-16 ***
Time:Transfer_2.4to2.4M	-0.166	0.030	-5.569	3e-8 ***
Time:Transfer_4to4M	-0.262	0.033	-7.884	3e-15 ***
Strain_C:Transfer2.4to2.4M	-1.950	0.139	-13.983	< 2e-16 ***
Strain_C:Transfer4to4M	-1.929	0.148	-13.040	< 2e-16 ***
Time:Strain_C:Transfer2.4to2.4M	0.494	0.042	11.748	< 2e-16 ***
Time:Strain_C:Transfer4to4M	0.306	0.045	6.859	7e-12 ***

GLM on population densities on days 1 to 5 from experiment 1, corresponding to maximal growth in this experiment (shaded area in Fig. 1). Our main interest is in the effect of Time and its interactions with other factors, which represent effects of these factors (here salinity transfer) on maximal population growth.

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Table S4: Initial decline and maximal growth rate of strain A populations after a hyper-osmotic shock against PCD inhibitor concentration gradient (experiment 2).

(A)	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr (> z)
Intercept (Strain A without inhibitor)	-1.231	0.119	-10.383	< 2e-16 ***
Inhibitor Concentration	0.150	0.045	3.321	9e-04 ***
(B)	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr (> z)
Intercept (Strain A without inhibitor, day 1)	7.952	0.123	64.448	< 2e-16 ***
Time	0.671	0.035	19.231	< 2e-16 ***
Inhibitor concentration	0.209	0.047	4.441	9e-06 ***
Time:Inhibitor Concentration	-0.021	0.013	-1.614	0.107

(A) GLM on population density on day 1 compared to the expected initial density. We tested the effect of a PCD inhibitor concentrations. **(B)** GLM on population densities on days 1-6, corresponding to maximal growth in this experiment (shaded area in Fig. S4). Our main interest is in Time and its interactions with the factor Inhibitor Concentration, which represent effects on population growth post-decline.

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Table S5: Initial decline against initial density and population growth phase (experiment 3).

(A)	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
Population density (day 1) for mid-exponential phase condition (4d)				
Intercept ($N_0 = 5,000$ cells/mL)	-1.080	0.102	-10.612	<2e-16 ***
N_0_{20000}	0.164	0.144	1.141	0.254
N_0_{30000}	0.143	0.143	0.996	0.319
Population density (day 1) for early-stationary phase condition (13d)				
Intercept ($N_0 = 5,000$ cells/mL)	-1.309	0.199	-6.583	5e-11 ***
N_0_{20000}	0.198	0.281	0.703	0.482
N_0_{30000}	0.294	0.281	1.045	0.296
Population density (day 1) for late-stationary phase condition (41d)				
Intercept ($N_0 = 5,000$ cells/mL)	-0.897	0.140	-6.409	1e-10 ***
N_0_{20000}	0.547	0.198	2.767	0.006 **
N_0_{30000}	0.805	0.198	4.073	5e-5 ***
(B)	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
Population density (day 1) for $N_0 = 5,000$ cells/mL				
Intercept (phase = 4d)	-1.080	0.113	-9.533	<2e-16 ***
Phase_13d	-0.230	0.160	-1.433	0.152
Phase_41d	0.182	0.160	1.139	0.255
Population density (day 1) for $N_0 = 20,000$ cells/mL				
Intercept (phase = 4d)	-0.916	0.158	-5.811	6e-09 ***
Phase_13d	-0.196	0.223	-0.879	0.380
Phase_41d	0.566	0.223	2.539	0.011 *
Population density (day 1) for $N_0 = 30,000$ cells/mL				
Intercept (phase = 4d)	-0.937	0.178	-5.265	1e-07 ***
Phase_13d	-0.079	0.252	-0.313	0.754
Phase_41d	0.845	0.252	3.358	8e-4 ***

(A) GLM on population density on day 1 relative to the expected initial density, testing for effects of initial density (N_0), separately for each condition of population growth phase, using only strain A. **(B)** Same GLM, but testing for the effect of population growth phase, separately for each condition of initial density (N_0), using only strain A from the experiment 3.

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Table S6: Maximal growth rate against initial density and population growth phase (experiment 3).

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr (> z)
Intercept (Strain A N ₀ = 5000 & phase = 4d on day 4)	6.39094	0.20734	30.823	< 2e-16 ***
Time	0.65079	0.0564	11.54	< 2e-16 ***
Strain_C	1.98935	0.29294	6.791	1.11e-11 ***
Phase_13d	-0.64078	0.2936	-2.182	0.029 *
Phase_41d	0.01446	0.28983	0.05	0.960
N ₀ _20000	1.80943	0.29292	6.177	7e-10 ***
N ₀ _30000	2.29943	0.2929	7.851	4e-15 ***
Time:Strain_C	-0.27583	0.0797	-3.461	0.001 ***
Time:Phase_13d	-0.01618	0.07983	-0.203	0.839
Time:Phase_41d	-0.232	0.06394	-3.629	3e-4 ***
Strain_C:Phase_13d	0.30059	0.41457	0.725	0.468
Strain_C:Phase_41d	-1.10379	0.40962	-2.695	0.007 **
Time:N ₀ _20000	-0.11006	0.07969	-1.381	0.167
Time:N ₀ _30000	-0.14041	0.07969	-1.762	0.078 .
Strain_C:N ₀ _20000	-0.34895	0.41402	-0.843	0.399
Strain_C:N ₀ _30000	-0.44318	0.41399	-1.07	0.284
Phase_13d:N ₀ _20000	-0.11154	0.41455	-0.269	0.788
Phase_41d:N ₀ _20000	0.44543	0.40953	1.088	0.277
Phase_13d:N ₀ _30000	-0.25146	0.4145	-0.607	0.544
Phase_41d:N ₀ _30000	0.86717	0.4095	2.118	0.034 *
Time:Strain_C:Phase_13d	0.04209	0.11277	0.373	0.709
Time:Strain_C:Phase_41d	0.18602	0.09037	2.059	0.040 *
Time:Strain_C:N ₀ _20000	0.08265	0.11266	0.734	0.463
Time:Strain_C:N ₀ _30000	0.12506	0.11265	1.11	0.267
Time:Phase_13d:N ₀ _20000	0.18438	0.11276	1.635	0.102
Time:Phase_41d:N ₀ _20000	0.06664	0.09035	0.738	0.461
Time:Phase_13d:N ₀ _30000	0.23504	0.11275	2.085	0.037 *
Time:Phase_41d:N ₀ _30000	0.03081	0.09035	0.341	0.733
Strain_C:Phase_13d:N ₀ _20000	0.17249	0.58573	0.294	0.768
Strain_C:Phase_41d:N ₀ _20000	-0.49085	0.57895	-0.848	0.397
Strain_C:Phase_13d:N ₀ _30000	0.31456	0.58569	0.537	0.591
Strain_C:Phase_41d:N ₀ _30000	-0.8172	0.57892	-1.412	0.158
Time:Strain_C:Phase_13d:N ₀ _20000	-0.19468	0.15937	-1.222	0.222
Time:Strain_C:Phase_41d:N ₀ _20000	-0.02966	0.12773	-0.232	0.816
Time:Strain_C:Phase_13d:N ₀ _30000	-0.26568	0.15936	-1.667	0.095 .
Time:Strain_C:Phase_41d:N ₀ _30000	-0.03044	0.12773	-0.238	0.812

GLM on population densities on days 2-5 or 4-9, corresponding to maximal growth in this experiment

(shaded area in Fig. S5). Our main interest is in Time and its interactions with other factors (Strain, Initial density, Population growth phase), which represent effects of these factors on maximal population growth post-decline.

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Table S7: Initial decline against nutrient abundance (experiment 4).

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	Population reduction (%)
Intercept (Strain A with Nutrient standard)	-1.615	0.084	-19.260	2e-12 ***	80
Strain_C	1.854	0.119	15.637	4e-11 ***	-27
Nutrient_limitation	0.601	0.119	5.069	1e-4 ***	64
Strain_C:Nutrient_limitation	-0.542	0.168	-3.231	0.005 **	-35

LM on log population density on day 1, estimated from the log whole-well fluorescence, relative to the

log expected initial density of strain C. We tested for the effect of nutrient limitation and strain identity.

We also reported the population size reduction.

Table S8: Maximal growth rate against nutrient abundance (experiment 4).

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
Intercept (Strain A with Nutrient standard)	8.011	0.185	43.204	< 2e-16 ***
Time	1.075	0.086	12.520	< 2e-16 ***
Strain_C	2.360	0.262	9.000	3e-12 ***
Nutrient_limitation	0.882	0.262	3.365	0.001 **
Time:Strain_C	-0.713	0.121	-5.877	3e-7 ***
Time:Nutrient_limitation	-0.378	0.121	-3.114	0.003 **
Strain_C:Nutrient_limitation	-0.774	0.371	-2.087	0.042 *
Time:Strain_C:Nutrient_limitation	0.318	0.172	1.853	0.070 .

LM on log population densities on days 1-3, corresponding to maximal growth in this experiment

(shaded area in Fig. S6), estimated from the log whole-well fluorescence. Our main interest is in Time

and its interactions with other factors (Strain, Nutrient abundance), which represent effects of these

factors on maximal population growth post-decline.

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Table S9: Initial decline against culture medium after a hyper-osmotic shock (experiment 5).

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	Population reduction (%)
Intercept (Strain A growing in control medium)	-1.471	0.051	-28.905	<2.00e-16 ***	77
Strain_C	1.600	0.072	22.290	<2.00e-16 ***	-14
Filtrate_A	0.163	0.072	2.264	0.026 *	73
Filtrate_C	-0.166	0.072	-2.308	0.021 *	81
Strain_C:Filtrate_A	-0.187	0.102	-1.845	0.065 .	6
Strain_C:Filtrate_C	0.150	0.102	1.480	0.139	-32

GLM on population density on day 1 relative to the expected initial density. We tested the effect of the different culture mediums and strain identity.

Table S10: Maximal growth rate against culture medium after a hyper-osmotic shock (experiment 5).

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
Intercept (Strain A growing in control medium at day 1)	8.607	0.071	121.296	<2e-16 ***
Time	0.638	0.021	29.819	<2e-16 ***
Strain_C	2.038	0.100	20.325	<2e-16 ***
Filtrate_A	0.356	0.100	3.547	4e-4 ***
Filtrate_C	-0.127	0.100	-1.265	0.206
Time:Strain_C	-0.374	0.030	-12.391	<2e-16 ***
Time:Filtrate_A	-0.046	0.030	-1.518	0.129
Time:Filtrate_C	0.043	0.030	1.431	0.153
Strain_C:Filtrate_A	-0.373	0.142	-2.629	0.009 **
Strain_C:Filtrate_C	0.118	0.142	0.834	0.404
Time:Strain_C:Filtrate_A	0.068	0.043	1.583	0.113
Time:Strain_C:Filtrate_C	-0.040	0.043	-0.929	0.353

GLM on population densities on days 1-5, corresponding to maximal growth in this experiment (shaded area in Fig. S7). Our main interest is in Time and its interactions with other factors (Strain, Culture medium), which represent effects on population growth post-decline.

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Table S11: Initial decline and maximal growth rate of strain C populations after a hyper-osmotic shock against culture medium (experiment 5).

(A)	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
Intercept (Strain C growing in control medium)	0.130	0.009	14.214	<2.00E-16 ***
Filtrate_A	-0.024	0.013	-1.860	0.058 .
Filtrate_C	-0.016	0.013	-1.230	0.219
(B)	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
Intercept (Strain C growing in control medium at day 1)	10.645	0.030	352.123	<2e-16 ***
Time	0.263	0.009	28.888	<2e-16 ***
Filtrate_A	-0.017	0.043	-0.392	0.695
Filtrate_C	-0.009	0.043	-0.203	0.839
Time:Filtrate_A	0.022	0.013	1.687	0.092 .
Time:Filtrate_C	0.004	0.013	0.276	0.783

(A) GLM on population density on day 1 compared to the expected initial density. We tested the effect of the different culture mediums. **(B)** GLM on population densities on days 1-5, corresponding to maximal growth in this experiment (shaded area in Fig. S7). Our main interest is in Time and its interactions with the factor Culture medium, which represent effects on strain C population growth post-decline.

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Table S12: Initial decline and Maximal growth rate against light intensity after a hyper-osmotic shock (experiment 6).

(A)	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	Population reduction (%)
Intercept (Strain A growing at 100 $\mu\text{mol.m}^{-2}.\text{s}^{-1}$ light)	-0.838	0.052	-16.043	<2e-16 ***	57
Strain_C	0.963	0.074	13.044	<2e-16 ***	-13
Light_200	-0.905	0.163	-5.536	3e-8 ***	82
Strain_C:Light_200	0.826	0.231	3.574	4e-4 ***	-159
(B)	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
Intercept (Strain A growing at 100 $\mu\text{mol.m}^{-2}.\text{s}^{-1}$ light on first day of exponential phase)	9.722	0.110	88.262	<2e-16 ***	
Time	0.429	0.029	14.855	<2e-16 ***	
Strain_C	0.719	0.156	4.619	4e-6 ***	
Light_200	-1.699	0.485	-3.504	5e-4 ***	
Time:Strain_C	-0.118	0.041	-2.878	0.004 **	
Time:Light_200	0.442	0.163	2.710	0.007 **	
Strain_C:Light_200	1.940	0.686	2.829	0.005 **	
Time:Strain_C:Light_200	-0.496	0.231	-2.150	0.032 *	

(A) GLM on population density on day 1 compared to the expected initial density. We tested the effect of the light intensity and strain identity. **(B)** GLM on population densities on days corresponding to maximal growth for each experiment (light experiment: shaded area in Fig. S8). Our main interest is in Time and its interactions with the factor Light, which represent effects on population growth post-decline.

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Table S13: Initial decline and maximal growth rate against successive shocks (experiment 7).

(A)	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	Population reduction (%)
Intercept (Strain A undergoing hyperosmotic shock 1)	-0.979	0.030	-32.403	<2.00E-16 ***	62
Strain_C	1.043	0.043	24.525	<2.00E-16 ***	-7
Shock_2	-0.404	0.043	-9.428	<2.00E-16 ***	75
Strain_C:Shock_2	0.430	0.062	6.920	4.52E-12 ***	-64
(B)	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)	
Intercept (Strain A undergoing hyperosmotic shock 1 at day 3)	7.501	0.115	65.501	<2e-16 ***	
Time	0.528	0.022	23.947	<2e-16 ***	
Strain_C	1.661	0.162	10.259	<2e-16 ***	
Shock_2	-0.055	0.162	-0.339	0.735	
Time:Strain_C	-0.246	0.031	-7.894	3e-15 ***	
Time:Shock_2	0.029	0.031	0.944	0.345	
Strain_C:Shock_2	0.031	0.236	0.133	0.894	
Time:Strain_C:Shock_2	-0.032	0.045	-0.696	0.486	

(A) GLM on population density on day 1 compared to the expected initial density. We tested the effect of the salinity fluctuations and strain identity. **(B)** GLM on population densities on days 3-7, corresponding to maximal growth in this experiment (shaded area in Fig. S9). Our main interest is in Time and its interactions with the factor Shock, which represent effects on population growth post-decline.

Supplementary material Figures

Figure S1: Cytometer estimation for live cells and apparently dead cells following a hyper-osmotic shock (experiment 1), in linear scale (A) and log scale (B). The apparently dead cells correspond to cells with much lower red fluorescence in cytometry, indicating that they are either dead or in poor condition (see Rescan et al. 2020). The number of apparently dead cells (in grey) is negligible relative to the number of disappearing live cells (in black) (A). In addition, both strains display an equivalent increase of apparently dead cells after the hyper-osmotic shock (B).

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Figure S2: Linear model between the cytometer estimation for density (in cells/mL) and the 685 nm fluorescence (spectrometer). Points correspond to the measurements made on day 2 to 4 from the nutrient assay (experiment 4). This LM led to the relationship:

$$Density_{population_{Fluo}} = 15.659 (Fluo - Fluo_{blank}) - 49182.885,$$

where $Fluo$ is fluorescence of the well, and $Fluo_{blank}$ is the corresponding measurement for a well that contains the culture medium but no cells.

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Figure S3. Preliminary test under different concentration of a PCD inhibitor for strain A under hyper-osmotic shock. Hyper-osmotic transfers occurred at time 0, and the first density measurements were made 15 minutes after the transfer, while the red square represents the expected initial density, predicted from dilution of the acclimated population. Filled symbols are averages over 2 replicates, error bars indicate the standard error, while lighter points are the raw densities.

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Figure S4. Demographic dynamics under different concentration of a PCD inhibitor. Iso-osmotic (left) or hyper-osmotic (right) transfers occurred at day 0, and the first measurements were made 1 hour after the transfer, while the red square represents the expected initial density, predicted from dilution of the acclimated population. The number of live *D. salina* cells per mL in each day is represented on the log scale, for strains A (dots, upper panels) and C (triangles, bottom panels). Filled symbols are averages over 3 replicates, error bars indicate the standard error, while lighter points are the raw densities. Note that the first 4 days of the upper right panel appear as Fig 2 in the main text.

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Figure S5: Influence of initial density and population growth phase on population dynamics following hyper-osmotic shock (experiment 3). Upper panels represent the demography of strain A, and lower panels the demography of strain C. Each panel from left to right represents a population growth phase: mid-exponential phase (4 days after transfer), early-stationary phase (13 days), and late stationary phase (41 days). Salinity rise occurs at time 0, and the expected initial densities are represented by red squares. The first observed point is measured 1 hour after the transfer. The y-axis is in log scale (live *D. salina* cells per mL). Filled symbols are averages over 3 replicates, with error bars representing standard error, while lighter symbols are the raw densities. The shaded areas correspond to the period of maximum exponential growth.

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Figure S6: Influence of nutrient level on population dynamics following hyper-osmotic shock (experiment 4). Estimates of population density are based on (A) whole-well fluorescence (685nm), or (B) cytometer counts. Salinity transfer occurs at time 0, and the first observed point is measured 1 hour after the transfer. The expected initial density is represented by a red square. Large darker symbols are mean over 5 replicates, while small lighter symbols are the raw densities. Standard growth conditions are shown in black, and nutrients limitation in grey. In A, the shaded area corresponds to the period of maximal exponential growth.

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Figure S7: Demographic dynamics in population filtrates (experiment 5). Each panel from left to right represents a salinity transfer, respectively an iso-osmotic transfer at intermediate salinity, a hyper-osmotic transfer and an iso-osmotic transfer at high salinity. Salinity transfer occurs at time 0, and the predicted initial density is represented by a red square. The first observed point is measured 1 hour after the transfer. The y-axis is in log scale (live *D. salina* cells per mL). Filled symbols are averages over 3 replicates. The shaded areas correspond to the period of maximum exponential growth.

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Figure S8: Demographic dynamics at higher intensity light (experiment 6). Salinity rise from 2.4M to 4M NaCl occurs at time 0, and mean expected initial densities per strain are represented by red symbols. The first observed point is measured 1 hour after the transfer. The y axis is in log scale (live *D. salina* cells per mL). Black symbols are means over 5 replicates, while smaller lighter symbols are raw densities. The shaded area corresponds to the period of maximum exponential growth.

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Figure S9: Demographic dynamics after one or two hyper-osmotic shocks (experiment 7). Salinity rise from 2.4M to 4M NaCl occurs at time 0, and the expected initial density is represented by a square. The first observed point is measured 1 hour after the transfer. The y axis is in log scale (live *D. salina* cells per mL). Filled symbols are means over 5 replicates, while smaller lighter symbols are raw densities. The shaded area corresponds to the period of maximum exponential growth.